

METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS AS A PREDICTOR OF CHEMISTRY PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS AMONG MSU-LANAO NATIONAL COLLEGE OF ARTS AND TRADES JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 9

Pages: 1097-1102

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2417

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13850408

Manuscript Accepted: 08-12-2024

Metacognitive Awareness as a Predictor of Chemistry Problem-Solving Skills among MSU-Lanao National College of Arts and Trades Junior High School Students

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between high school students' metacognitive awareness—specifically in planning, monitoring, and evaluation—and their Chemistry problem-solving skills, framed by Polya's four steps of problem-solving: understanding the problem, devising a plan, implementing the plan, and re-evaluation. Conducted with students from MSU-Lanao National College of Arts and Trades (MSU-LNCAT) during the Academic Year 2023-2024, the research utilized a non-experimental quantitative design with a predictive correlational approach. Data were collected using the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) and the Chemistry Problem-Solving Test Questionnaire (PSTQ). Descriptive statistics and Kendall's Tau Correlation were applied for analysis, revealing that while students demonstrated high metacognitive awareness and strong problem-solving skills, no significant correlation was found between these variables (p -value = 0.566, Kendall's Tau = 0.046). This unexpected result suggests that further investigation is needed to explore the factors influencing the relationship between metacognitive awareness and Chemistry problem-solving skills.

Keywords: *chemistry, metacognitive awareness, problem-solving, cognitive skills*

Introduction

Science is applied knowledge with a significant impact on everyday activities. It is crucial for both individuals and nations to survive and meet global economic requirements, highlighting the importance of science subjects. The world's wealth and economic development increasingly depend on the science workforce, underscoring the value of science education.

One of the essential branches of science is Chemistry. Chemistry has been fundamental to the development of science, as it involves the mixing of elements to create new materials and alloys, driving innovation and technological progress. Chemistry is integral to producing various products crucial for daily use, such as soap, shampoo, detergents, and food items like yeast and vinegar. Furthermore, understanding the chemical composition of the human body is vital for diagnosing, treating, and preventing diseases. Chemistry's interconnection with other subjects underscores its foundational role in the development of various sciences. Employing the scientific method, Chemistry encourages students to think critically and analytically. Consequently, Chemistry not only aids in national progress but also contributes to developing mentally healthy individuals.

Alavi, Hoseini (2009) stressed that a particular attention toward the factors effective on learning chemistry is required because of the ever-increasing development of information and knowledge concerning chemistry and its deep relation with mathematics, physics and its vast application in the subjects related to empirical sciences (biology, medicine, pharmacy and so on) and technical engineering sciences (chemistry engineering, petro chemistry, metallurgy, and etc.).

Furthermore, little research has compared the importance of different factors affecting students' individual interest in school science lessons.

Research Questions

The study's main objective was to determine the significance of metacognitive awareness on Chemistry problem-solving skills among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following objectives:

1. To determine the extent of metacognitive awareness among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students in terms of:
 - 1.1. planning;
 - 1.2. monitoring; and
 - 1.3. evaluation.
2. To determine the level of Chemistry problem-solving skills among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students in terms of:
 - 2.1. understanding the problem;
 - 2.2. devising a plan;
 - 2.3. implementing a plan, and
 - 2.4. re-evaluation.
3. To determine the significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and Chemistry problem-solving skills among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students and
4. To determine what domain in metacognitive awareness significantly predicts the Chemistry problem-solving skill among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students.

Literature Review

Chemistry is instrumental in developing cognitive skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and systematic analysis, applicable across various disciplines and real-world situations. In the 21st century, metacognitive skills—such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating one's thinking processes—are essential for academic and personal success. Studies indicate that students who employ metacognitive strategies achieve better learning outcomes. Metacognitive skills involve higher-order thinking and are crucial for fostering advanced cognitive processes [Lai, E.R., 2011; Livingston, 2003; Rahman, 2010].

In a high school setting, chemistry introduces fundamental scientific concepts and enhances logical and analytical thinking. It encourages creativity through experimental design and hypothesis testing and fosters collaboration through group work. Students in a chemistry lab must manage extensive information, including instructions on equipment use, safety protocols, and theoretical concepts. This complex environment can be challenging, but it is an excellent opportunity for students to apply metacognitive skills by reading, predicting, reflecting, and considering alternative solutions during problem-solving tasks [Agustian et al., 2017; Brederode et al., 2020; Seery et al., 2019].

Encouraging students to use metacognitive strategies, such as those outlined by Kusaka & Ndiokubwayo (2022) and Siagian et al. (2019), can help them navigate the intricate learning environment of a chemistry laboratory and improve their problem-solving abilities.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs a non-experimental quantitative research design with a predictive correlational approach to predict the association between variables based on their observed values (Nurse Key, 2017). Unlike experimental research, correlational studies do not establish causality but identify the existence and strength of the relationship between variables (Karasar, 2017). In a predictive correlational design, the dependent variable (or outcome variable) is the variable being predicted. In contrast, the independent variable (or predictor variable) is used to estimate the value of the dependent variable (Ivy Panda, 2022).

In this study, the Chemistry problem-solving skills of students serve as the dependent variable, and metacognitive awareness is the independent variable used to predict these skills. Kendall's Tau correlation, a non-parametric correlation measure, was employed to assess the degree of association between the ordinal or ranked and continuous variables (Khamis, 2008).

Respondents

The respondents for this study were all Grade 9 students at MSU-Lanao National College of Arts and Trades (MSU-LNCAT) for the Academic Year 2023-2024. Stratified random sampling was utilized to select the respondents. This method involves dividing the population into subgroups or strata based on shared attributes or characteristics (Hayes, 2022). For this study, the strata were defined by the students' sections.

The researchers personally distributed and collected the printed questionnaires on the MSU-LNCAT campus. Respondents were provided with printed informed consent before receiving the questionnaires, which explained their right to participate voluntarily. They were advised that participation was discretionary and that they could withdraw from the study by informing the researchers. During the distribution process, the researchers were available to address any questions or concerns from the respondents. Respondents were instructed to provide honest, clear, and complete answers and were allotted one hour to complete the questionnaire.

Instrument

This study utilized the Metacognitive Awareness Inventory (MAI) to gather quantitative data on respondents' metacognitive awareness, explicitly focusing on their planning, monitoring, and evaluation strategies. Developed by Schraw and Dennison (1994) and later adapted by Nahil M. Aljaberi and Eman Gheith (2015) in their study "University Students' Level of Metacognitive Thinking and their Ability to Solve Problems," the MAI originally comprised two main components and eight subcomponents of metacognition. However, five subcomponents were removed in the current study to align with the research objectives and indicators.

The MAI is a 20-item self-report questionnaire using a 5-point Likert scale, where students rate their agreement with statements related to their metacognitive processes. The scale ranges from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree. The interpretation of each rating scale is detailed in Table 2.1, and composite scores for metacognitive awareness were computed to assess how metacognition predicts Chemistry problem-solving skills. Mode values were also used to interpret responses, as illustrated in Table 2.2 verbally.

In Aljaberi and Gheith's (2015) study, the MAI demonstrated high reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.952 for the overall scale, based on a sample of 50 students. The MAI is recognized as a reliable psychometric measure for metacognitive awareness, with an overall alpha of 0.90 (Schraw & Dennison, 1994; Hughes, 2019). Reliability coefficients for the three metacognitive indicators in the MAI were 0.83 for planning, 0.88 for monitoring, and 0.81 for evaluation (Aljaberi & Gheith, 2015).

To assess problem-solving skills, the Problem-Solving Test Questionnaire (PSTQ) was adapted by the researchers from Marlon T. Siniguan (2017).

Results and Discussion

The Extent of Metacognitive Awareness among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 Students

Table 1. *The Extent of Metacognitive Awareness among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 Students in Terms of Planning, Monitoring, and Evaluation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mode</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Planning	4	High
Monitoring	4	High
Evaluation	4	High
Overall	4	High

Table 1 summarizes the extent of metacognitive awareness regarding planning, monitoring, and evaluation.

Planning. Planning refers to a phase in students' metacognitive awareness, which involves choosing the right strategy and allocating resources that affect their performance. In the adapted MAI, Planning comprised of seven-item statements. As presented, the extent of students' metacognitive awareness in terms of planning is 4, which is described as high. This means that the extent of metacognitive awareness of Grade 9 students in terms of planning is much exhibited.

Monitoring. Monitoring refers to awareness of student's understanding and task performance. In the adapted MAI, Monitoring comprised of seven-item statements. As presented, the extent of students' metacognitive awareness in monitoring is 4, which is described as high. This means that the extent of metacognitive awareness of Grade 9 students in terms of monitoring is much exhibited.

Evaluation. Evaluation refers to product assessment and regulating a student's learning process. In the adapted MAI, the evaluation is comprised of six-item statements. As presented, the extent of the student's metacognitive awareness in evaluation is 4, which is described as high. This means that the extent of metacognitive awareness of Grade 9 students in evaluation is much exhibited.

Overall Metacognitive Awareness. Using the data of the abovementioned indicators, the average extent of metacognitive awareness among Grade 9 students is 4, and described as high. This means that the extent of metacognitive awareness among Grade 9 students in terms of planning, monitoring, and evaluation is much exhibited.

The study by Aurah et al. (2011), in which most students scored high on the MAI scale, supports this finding. This indicates that most students have a high level of metacognitive awareness, which is advantageous for their learning and has the potential to improve the awareness of their learning in the classroom significantly. As per Siagian et al. (2019), there is a need for awareness that students must have at every step of their thinking to improve their metacognitive ability, primarily involving planning, monitoring, and evaluation.

The Level of Chemistry Problem-Solving Skills among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 Students

Table 2. *The Level of Chemistry Problem-solving Skills among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 Students in Terms of Understanding the Problem, Devising a Plan, Implementing a Plan, and Re-evaluation*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive</i>
Understanding the Problem	2.69	0.4300	Very High
Devising a Plan	2.74	0.4181	Very High
Implementing a Plan	2.65	0.4300	Very High
Re-evaluation	2.45	0.4763	Very High
Overall	2.63	0.4515	Very High

Table 2 summarizes the problem-solving skills in understanding the problem, devising a plan, implementing a plan, and re-evaluating.

Understanding the problem. Understanding the problem is the first step in Polya's problem-solving steps, where students must understand the meaning of a problem statement, identify the known, the unknown, and the relationship between them, and recognize all concepts needed for solving the problem. As presented, most students have very high problem-solving skills in understanding the problem, with a mean of 2.69 and a standard deviation of 0.4300. This means that the level of problem-solving skills among Grade 9 students in understanding the problem is very much exhibited.

Devising a Plan. Devising a plan is the second step in Polya's problem-solving steps, where students must clarify the relations between parts of the problem, combine previously learned knowledge to develop thoughts for solving a problem and develop a plan. As presented, most students have very high problem-solving skills in devising a plan, with a mean of 2.74 and a standard deviation of 0.4181. This means that the level of problem-solving skills among Grade 9 students in devising a plan is very much exhibited.

Implementing a Plan. Implementing a plan is the third step in Polya's problem-solving steps, where students carry out or execute all calculations identified in the previous plan. As presented, most of the students have a very high level of problem-solving skills in re-evaluation, with a mean of 2.45 and a standard deviation of 0.4763. This means that the level of problem-solving skills among Grade

9 students in re-evaluation is very much exhibited.

Re-evaluation. Re-evaluation is the last step in Polya's problem-solving steps, where students will look again at the answer and check the accuracy of answers with questions. As presented, most of the students have a very high level of problem-solving skills in re-evaluation, with a mean of 2.45 and a standard deviation of 0.4763. This means that the level of problem-solving skills among Grade 9 students in re-evaluation is very much exhibited.

Overall Problem-solving Skills. Using the data of the abovementioned indicators, students' average level of problem-solving skills in terms of understanding the problem, devising a plan, implementing a plan, and re-evaluating is 2.63, described as very high, with a standard deviation of 0.4515. This means that the level of problem-solving skills among Grade 9 students is very much exhibited.

The standard deviation of the abovementioned indicators shows that devising a plan with the highest mean of 2.74 among the other indicators has the lowest standard deviation of 0.4181. On the other hand, the re-evaluation with the lowest mean of 2.45 has the highest standard deviation of 0.4763. This implies that students' problem-solving skills in re-evaluation are more dispersed or varied than the other indicators. Because the four indicators have closer standard deviation values, the coefficients of variation are presented in Table 3 to compare their relative variability.

Based on the table above, the coefficient of variation for understanding the problem is 15.99%; devising a plan is 15.26%; implementing a plan is 16.23%; and re-evaluation is 19.44%.

Table 3. *Coefficient of Variation for Chemistry Problem-solving Skills in Terms of Understanding the Problem, Devising a Plan, Implementing a Plan, and Re-evaluation*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation (%)
Understanding the Problem	2.69	0.4300	15.99
Devising a Plan	2.74	0.4181	15.26
Implementing a Plan	2.65	0.4300	16.23
Re-evaluation	2.45	0.4763	19.44

Since the coefficient of variation for re-evaluation is more significant than that of understanding the problem, devising a plan, and implementing a plan, the re-evaluation in problem-solving skills is more dispersed, which means that the Chemistry problem-solving skills of Grade 9 students in terms of the re-evaluation are less consistent than the other indicators, followed by the skill in implementing a plan.

The present study noted that re-evaluation followed by implementing a plan are two of the most dispersed indicators of Chemistry problem-solving skills. This could be because some students look back at their answers but have written and checked problem-solving results inconsistently in all situations, which is the same possible instance that goes with implementing a plan.

In addition, according to Aksu (1984) (cited in Sevgi & Caglikose, 2019), some students need to check their answers after resolving a problem and coming up with a solution. The importance of students mastering Chemistry concepts to lessen errors in solving mathematical problems and constructing mathematical equations in a well-developed manner to get to the correct solution.

Correlation between Metacognitive Awareness and Problem-solving Skills

Table 4. *Kendall's Tau Correlation Coefficient between Metacognitive Awareness and Chemistry Problem-solving Skills*

	Kendall's Tau	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Metacognitive Awareness Chemistry Problem-solving Skills	0.046	0.566	Fail to Reject H01	Not significant

The table above shows that the p-value (0.566) is more significant than the significance level ($\alpha=0.05$), Fail to Reject H01, which reveals no significant relationship between the students' extent of metacognitive awareness and their problem-solving skills. This means that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between the extent of metacognitive awareness and the level of problem-solving skills in MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students.

It is also noted in Table 4 that a correlation coefficient of 0.046 indicates no correlation between the students' extent of metacognitive awareness and their problem-solving skills. This means that the Grade 9 students' level of Chemistry problem-solving skills is not affected or associated with the extent of their metacognitive awareness.

These findings are consistent with the study of Coutinho (2006), which revealed that metacognitive awareness is not helpful for students performing problem-solving tasks, as students with a higher level of metacognitive awareness did not perform any better than those with a lower level of metacognitive awareness.

The findings of this study, on the other hand, are entirely unexpected because it is somewhat expected that the metacognitive awareness of students helps them to solve mathematical problems better (Casaig, 2019) and that if metacognitive students are high, then their problem-solving skills are also high (Izzati & Mahmudi, 2018). This result is inconsistent with the study of Hassan and Rahman (2017),

who assert that there is, in fact, a positive, significant relationship between problem-solving skills and metacognitive awareness. Based on their study, metacognitive awareness plays a vital role in ensuring the success of the Chemistry problem-solving process. It is also added that problem-solving entails understanding and controlling more complicated metacognitive processes, such as planning, monitoring, and evaluation, in addition to attempting to obtain the correct answer (Hassan & Rahman, 2017). This is parallel to the study of Sevgi and Karakaya (2020), which concluded that metacognitive awareness levels in students show a positive and significant relationship with problem-solving skills, emphasizing that metacognitive awareness abilities are similar to problem-solving steps. Students use them when defining variables in a problem and determining which technique to use.

This inconsistency of the results sheds light on the need for further studies better to understand the relationship between metacognitive awareness and Chemistry problem-solving skills, considering the factors that contributed to the two variables having no significant relationship.

Unfortunately, since the result of the correlation analysis found that there is no significant relationship between the student's metacognitive awareness and their level of Chemistry problem-solving skills, this indicates that researchers cannot proceed with the regression analysis because it will not meet the assumptions for ordinal-continuous regression.

Conclusions

This study conducted surveys and test questionnaires with MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students to determine the significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and chemistry problem-solving skills. Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The extent of metacognitive awareness among Grade 9 students in planning, monitoring, and evaluation is high. This indicates that most students have a high level of metacognitive awareness. By this means, the researchers concluded that most MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students highly exhibited metacognitive awareness. This result is consistent with the Meta-components of Intelligence Theory of Robert Sternberg (1988), which are the complex processes of selecting one or more approaches, controlling them, and coordinating the various approaches, composed of planning, monitoring, and evaluating courses of thinking and action. With this, empowerment, motivation, and increased relationships of metacognitive awareness can be supported by encouraging good participation in planning, monitoring, and evaluation.

The level of problem-solving skills among Grade 9 students in understanding the problem, devising a plan, implementing a plan, and re-evaluation is very high. This indicates that most students have a very high level of problem-solving skills. By this means, the researcher concluded that most Grade 9 students in MSU-LNCAT highly exhibited problem-solving skills. However, concerning the coefficients of variation, it is revealed that the re-evaluation of students' problem-solving skills is more dispersed than understanding the problem, devising a plan, and implementing a plan. This could mean that students write and check their answers inconsistently or skip checking their answer solutions.

That reveals that there is no significant relationship between the students' extent of metacognitive awareness and their level of problem-solving skills. This finding shows that the extent of metacognitive awareness does not affect the level of problem-solving skills of students. This means that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between the extent of metacognitive awareness and the level of problem-solving skills among MSU-LNCAT Grade 9 students. This result is inconsistent with the Meta-components of Intelligence Theory of Robert Sternberg (1988), which states that meta-components are higher-order executive processes used in planning, monitoring, and evaluating one's problem-solving. Since it is also revealed that metacognitive awareness does not influence problem-solving skills, the result is also inconsistent with the Cognitive Developmental Theory of Jean Piaget (1973), which implies that learners must reach higher levels of reflection of their actions by thinking about their thinking, simply metacognitive awareness, in order to justify their use of metacognition in problem-solving.

However, the nature of the correlation between metacognitive awareness and problem-solving skills is a type that makes this finding entirely unexpected; if the metacognitive of students is high, then their problem-solving skills are also high (Izzati & Mahmudi, 2018). The difficulty level of the problem-solving test questions, which do not likely coincide with the students' extent of awareness of their metacognitive ability, contributed to the two variables having no significant relationship. This finding does not necessarily imply that there is indeed no significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and problem-solving skills; other factors could contribute to this result. Hence, this highlights the need for further studies in these areas.

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